

PHYSIOTHERAPY IN PERSONS OVER 80 YEARS OF AGE

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Abstract

Persons older than 80 are a significant group of patients in outpatient clinics. The aim of the study was to evaluate the effect of physiotherapeutic treatment of pain experienced by geriatric patients and to evaluate the basic activities in their daily lives before and after the 10 days improvement of the elderly during ambulatory treatment. The study was conducted at the Medical Center in Strzelin. The study group consisted of patients over 80 years of age (18 women and 6 men) with an average age of 86 ± 8 , with pain caused by osteoarthritis, sciatica, rheumatoid arthritis, pericarditis and peri-arthritis. It has been shown that physiotherapeutic treatment in people over 80 significantly reduces feelings of pain and does not affect the improvement of basic activities in everyday life..

Key words: Physiotherapy treatment, feeling pain, people over 80 years old.

Introduction

As average life expectancy so has the number of elderly people. The general process of physical aging involves pathological lesions, problems with bodily functions, and morbidity of different systems and organs which lead to walking disorders and problems with personal activities. The situations described have an impact on the quality of elderly people's lives and limit their physical activity. Those people need medical and physiotherapy treatment and it is a challenge for doctors and physiotherapists. It is necessary to select a proper programme of activities for people who belong to the mentioned age group (1). No papers that refer to physiotherapy treatment dedicated to elderly people have been found so far. That is why the effects of physical therapy of people over 80 have been evaluated during outpatient treatment.

Aim

People over 80 are a large group of patients at outpatient clinics. They take part in individual or group activities, massages as well as

physiotherapeutic treatment. The aim of this article is to evaluate the influence of physiotherapeutic treatment on pain and basic activities connected with everyday life before and after 10 days of activities selected for elderly people during outpatient treatment.

Reference methods and materials

The examinations were conducted at the Medical Center in Strzelin. The examined group comprised patients over the age of 80 (18 women and 6 men), the average age 86 ± 8 . Patients suffered from pain caused by osteoarthritis, sciatica, rheumatoid arthritis, ankylosing spondylitis and peri-arthritis inflammation. Examinations were carried out by a physiotherapist. The eligibility criteria consists of a referral form for physiotherapy treatment, the patient's consent for taking part in examinations and obtaining a minimum of 4 points on an AMTS test. For the purposes of examinations patients have been evaluated according to Katza's (ADL) scale to evaluate the basic activities of their everyday life. Hodgkinson's test (AMTS) was applied, which evaluates the mental

capacity of patients and Borga's 10-scale which evaluates the level of experienced pain (Tab. 1, 2, 3).

Katza's scale (ADL) evaluates 6 basic everyday life activities to determine patients'

physical capacity. In examining patients according to this scale, the support of other people has been taken into consideration (Tab. 1).

Tab.1. Katza's scale – ADL (evaluation scale of basic every day life activities).

	INDEPENDENT - YES	INDEPENDENT - NO
1. BATHING	1	0
2. DRESSING/UNDRESSING	1	0
3. USING THE LAVATORY	1	0
4. GETTING OUT OF BED AND MOBILITY IN AN ARMCHAIR	1	0
5. INDEPENDENT EATING	1	0
6. CONTROLLED DISCHARGE OF STOOLS AND PASSING OF URINE	1	0

Score:

- 5 – 6 – non - disabled people
- 3 – 4 – moderately disabled people
- =< 2 – considerably disabled people

Hodgkinson's test evaluates patients' mental capacity. Through simple questions and orders the awareness of the patients and their

memory is controlled. The test described was carried out only once in order to qualify patients for the conducted examinations. The Patient had to obtain 4 or more points to be assured that the received answers evaluated according to Katz's scale and Borg's 10 scales were reliable (Tab. 2).

Tab.2. Mental capacity test according to Hodgkinson (AMTS).

How old are you?
What time is it?
Please repeat and try to remember the address you are going to hear – Gruszkowa Street 42.
What year is it?
What is your address?
When were you born?
What year did the Second World War start?
What is the name of the Polish president?
Please count backwards from 20 to 1.
Please repeat the address that you heard.

Single correct answer - 1 point, max. 10 points.

- >6 – non – disabled person
- 4-6 – moderately disabled person
- 0-3 – considerably disabled person

Hodgkinson's test shows that 17 patients are non – disabled, but 7 patients are moderately disabled (Ryc.1).

Ryc.1. Evaluation of mental capacity, according to Hodgkinson's Test, patients undergoing physiotherapeutic treatment.

Borga's scale is used for subjective measurement of the patients' degree of pain. The scale presented was used in order to obtain information about whether physical treatment lowers pain (Tab. 3).

Tab.3. 10 – Borga's 10 grade scale

BORGAS SCALE USED FOR SUBJECTIVE MEASUREMENT OF A PATIENT'S DEGREE OF PAIN	
10 GRADE SCALE	
0	no pain
0,5	light pain
1	mild pain
2	annoying pain
3	moderate pain
4	significant pain
5	intense pain
6	
7	severe pain
8	
9	
10	severe pain, unable to perform tasks

Having qualified patients for physiotherapeutic treatment, the length of rehabilitation (10 days) was applied. This consists of physiotherapeutic treatment such as: a laser 1 time per day for about 5 minutes, a magnetic field 1 time per day for about 15 minutes, interferential currents 1 time per day for about 15 minutes, diadynamic currents 1 per day for about 15 minutes, TENS 1 per day for about 15 minutes, sollux 1 per day for about 15 minutes, cryotherapy 1 per day for about 3 minutes and ultrasound 1 per day for about 3

minutes on different parts of the body for example: lumbar spine, knee joint and shoulder girdle.

Physiotherapy treatment was used for 10 days according to the requirement of the National Health Fund.

At the beginning and at the end of the physiotherapeutic treatment programme that lasts 10 days, every patient took a subjective measurement of the degree of pain according to Borga's scale and evaluated the basic activities of their everyday life according to Katz's scale.

All patients finished selected the programme.

The data collected has been statistically analyzed. For each parameter the mean value and standard deviation have been charged. The materiality level within the group has been determined by using the T Student's Test.

Results

During the research, subjective measurement of pain degree according to Borga's scale and basic activities of everyday life according to Katza's scale have been analyzed. The mean value of examined indicators and average value were compared before and after physiotherapeutic treatment.

The study showed that the average value of pain experienced before physiotherapeutic treatment in the group of women was 9.5, but after physiotherapy treatment it is 8.5. The level of pain experienced lowered about 10.5% and it is statistically relevant.

In a group of men the level of experienced pain was 10, but after physiotherapeutic treatment 9. The level of experienced pain lowered about 10 % and it is statistically relevant (Tab. 4).

Tab.4. Evaluation of experienced pain before and after physiotherapeutic treatment.

Evaluation of experienced pain			
Before Women - Men		After Women - Men	
9	10	7	8
9	10	9	9
9	10	9	10
9	10	8	9
9	10	10	8
9	10	7	10
9		8	
9		9	
9		10	
10		7	
10		8	
10		9	
10		10	
10		7	
10		8	
10		9	
10		9	
10		9	
9		8	
9		9	
9		8	
10		8	
10		9	
10		9	

Patients' capacity for dealing with everyday life activities before and after physiotherapy has not changed (Ryc. 2).

Ryc.2. Evaluation of dealing with everyday life before and after physiotherapy.

Discussion

The aim of physiotherapy among elderly people is to improve physical capacity in everyday life as well as lower experienced pain. According to the Polish model of comprehensive physiotherapy presented by prof. Wiktor Dega (1) and guidelines that refer to individual rehabilitation of the geriatric, care should be individualized considering the existing distortions (2).

Examinations conducted by Marek Żak refer to the rehabilitation of people over 80 years old considering different types of physical activities with satisfactory results. Physical capacity has been improved significantly (3). Analyzed results of basic every day activities have not improved but the level of experienced pain has decreased according to Borga's scale.

Another form of physiotherapy is occupational therapy. Research conducted by Dr. Adrianna Maria Borowicz shows positive results of physical capacity in the area of basic activities of everyday life. What is more, occupational therapy enables participation in community life, the develop of passions and has influence on mental state, decreasing tension

and levels of stress and promoting a healthy lifestyle (4).

The review of research conducted by Agnieszka Borzym shows that highly efficient risk reduction of falls indicates properly selected exercises that have an influence on proper body poise, better balance, strong muscles and better physical capacity in everyday life (5).

Physical treatment exercises have influence on decreasing feelings of anxiety about falling, improved blood flow, ameliorate the symptoms of depression, and improve the quality of sleeping which is reflected in patients' well-being (6).

On the basis of studies it is assumed that physical treatment has a positive influence on reduced levels of experienced pain but it does not affect the physical capacity of elderly people (7).

Results of research conducted by the authors of this article and results presented by other authors are evidence of the need to apply comprehensive physiotherapy to geriatric patients in order to obtain better physical capabilities. The aim of detailed recordings and reviews of the effects of physiotherapy on longevity, which involves physical treatment,

kinesiotherapy and occupational therapy, are necessarily for further examinations of geriatric patients who suffer from pain caused by osteoarthritis, ischias, rheumatoid arthritis, ankylosing spondylitis and periarticular inflammation (1, 7).

Conclusion

1. It has been proved that physiotherapeutic treatment of geriatric patients over 80 years old significantly decreases experienced pain.

2. It has been pointed out that physiotherapy treatment does not have any influence on improvement of basic activities connected with everyday life.

3. Kinesiotherapy and occupational therapy is a favorable form of rehabilitation amongst geriatric patients.

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